

BorderForce

**BorderForce 2nd
Newsletter**

Welcome Back!

In this **2nd edition** of the BorderForce **Newsletter**, we are pleased to share an overview of the project's recent achievements and upcoming activities.

Since our last issue, the project successfully completed its first reporting period, along with a successful EU Review. Significant progress was also achieved through integrated testing activities and the validation of key technologies, while consortium partners actively participated in a number of events and dissemination activities, further increasing the project's visibility and impact.

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Our Recent Meetups

A quick look at our latest participation in events and project meetings

April
2026

BorderForce project presented at **RSCy2026** – *the 12th International Conference on Remote Sensing and Geoinformation of the Environment*, held in Paphos, Cyprus (27-29 April 2026).

[Geosystems Hellas S.A.](#) presented the project’s progress and its contribution to enhance situational awareness, automated border surveillance, and flexible security solutions, in a presentation entitled:

“BorderForce: Flexible System Extending Automated Border Surveillance by Increased Situational Awareness Adaptable to Uncertain Times with Unforeseen Events.”

BorderForce showcased at the World Border Security Congress 2026 in Vienna, Austria (13-15 April 2026).

[AIT \(Austrian Institute of Technology\)](#) together with [MOI Slovakian Ministry of Interior](#) during the event participated in a discussion regarding innovations in the field of border surveillance and advanced technologies for border management.

Another participation of **BorderForce** project was in **RISE-SD 2026 - Research and Innovation Symposium for European Security and Defense** in Varna, Bulgaria (15-16 April 2026).

[AIT \(Austrian Institute of Technology\)](#) presented the progress of the **BorderForce** project regarding the enhancement of border surveillance through improved situational awareness and innovative security solutions for uncertain and evolving environments.

March
2026

The BorderForce Consortium and Review meeting, held on 16-19 March, in Athens, Greece.

These days provided a valuable opportunity for the partners to discuss the progress of the project's activities in preparation for the review meeting, as well as to plan the next steps, such as the demonstrations in Bulgaria and Lithuania.

BorderForce project was presented at **Borderless Border Management Conference 2026** in Narva, Estonia (5-6 March 2026).

During conference, [VTT Technical Research Centre](#) presented the **BorderForce** project, highlighting the importance of collaborative European research and innovation for next-generation border security.

Our Tech Progress

All technologies developed within the project were successfully implemented, enabling the system to reach TRL 5 following the first integrated test conducted at the Securiton Deutschland SecuriDrone Test Center in November 2025. Additional testing activities further supported the maturation of the system and the completion of subsequent development steps.

*The first integration test was implemented on 24-28 November 2025 at **Securiton Deutschland** SecuriDrone Test Center, in Germany.*

The BorderForce partners integrated and tested the different components including command-and-control software, sensors, communication links and unmanned aerial platforms to verify the performance of the integrated system under realistic operational workflows.

The second integration test took place on 18-21 May 2026 at the SecuriDrone Test Center hosted by our partner Securiton in Germany

The BorderForce consortium validated the key system's components and evaluated its performance.

The successful completion of these two integration tests marks the achievement of important milestones in the project, paving the way for the upcoming operational testing activities in Bulgaria scheduled for 29 June – 2 July 2026.

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Synergies with other projects

A new synergy has been established with [COLOSSUS](#), a Horizon Europe project coordinated by [TecnoVeritas](#), with [Q-PLAN](#) International acting as Communication and Dissemination Manager. COLOSSUS focuses on strengthening the security and resilience of port infrastructure through the use of autonomous systems, advanced sensors, and AI-driven analytics.

Our plans for the next months

In the upcoming period, our activities will focus on participation in conferences, the publication of research papers in scientific journals and the development of new synergies with other projects.

In addition, preparations are currently underway for the **Operational Testing activities** scheduled for July in Bulgaria, as well as for the **Field Trial** planned for November 2026.

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